

CHRISTIAN RELIGIOUS ICONOCLASM IN CURBING IMMORALITY AMONG STUDENT TEACHERS FOR PEACE AND ALLEVIATION OPTIONS.

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Abstract: *Government with their many religious organizations have gone far in fighting against crime and indiscipline but despite their costly efforts immoral living are seen to be predominant among students in schools and colleges. This menace became more noticeable when you trace it to the poor teaching of Chastain Religious Studies and moral instructions, especially in most communities, schools and colleges. The method is descriptive in addressing this all important matter. Functional theory by Durkheim was applied as a framework. The central objective of this study is to reduce the religious violence and immorality among individual members of the society with particular reference to students thereby shaping the future with virtues and moral standards. Findings include that unqualified teachers make use of outdated method of teaching, they lack instructional materials, and also use outdated curriculum in teaching and learning of Christian religious Studies. There is always the tendency that the inability of students to understanding the teaching methods employed by the teachers, bad teacher/ students relationships, and lack of instructional materials are responsible for students' behavioral threat. Beyond the school system, there are several ancient and outdated religious practices in most of the communities of faith, the government and other educational owners' syndrome, and also other people's religious influences etc. However, the provision of audio visual materials, an urgent request or calls for religious cleansing, employments of qualified teachers, provision of textbooks, and/or availing updated curriculum to support religious centers, schools and colleges are the highlighted solutions to most identified problems in the owning, the practice, teaching and learning of Christian religion. Hence, Christian religious studies has a lot of impacts to shaping the physical, mental, moral, social and religious thoughts of the youths if caught up from the school level. And, religious iconoclasm when applied in the knowing, learning and practice of Christian*

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religion would be an inroad development towards achieving coherency, oneness, peace and other societal cum developmental alleviation options. This study concludes that religious iconoclasm has a lot to contribute to the curbing of unruly behavior, indiscipline and immoral living. Finally, some useful recommendations were made for an access to materials, contributions to knowledge and also for further research.

INTRODUCTION

The high level of moral decadence and insurgencies in Nigerian nation is a proof that there is poor Christian religious teaching in communities and in the school system. Although that educational body in Nigeria are owned by either the private persons, cooperate organizations and/or the government, the quality of students and teachers in most schools are shadow of themselves. The quality of Christian religious' graduates produced to teach others in some tertiary institutions are not helpful or employable thereby making morality not possible and mostly impracticable in schools and colleges. In schools, students are seen to be involved in such things as examination malpractice, indecent dressing, drug abuse, wait-and-take admissions, cultism and other unruly behaviors. And, for the society to survive and strive, there is need to go back to the drawing board via religious iconoclasm.

Christian Religious Studies (CRS) as one of the religious subjects taught in secondary schools and colleges in Nigeria takes a central position in ensuring moral and spiritual wellbeing of individuals in the society. The key roles of Christian Religious Studies in equipping the individuals and ensuring high level of morality is

made clear in the objectives of CRS at the Senior Secondary level which include; to provide more opportunities for Nigerian youths to learn more about God thereby developing their faith in God; to enable the youths to accept Christ as their savior; to help the youths develop Christian attitude and moral values (such as humility, respect, love, and justice, etc); to instill in the youths the spirit of tolerance , reconciliation ,peaceful co-existence and non-violence as well as to develop and foster in the youths the spirit of respect for all people and human life (Universal Basic Education Curriculum (UBA), 2013).

Moreover, it is possible to assume that without effective religious studies/teaching, Nigerian nation may likely end up in conflict, religious crisis, insurgencies and social unrest among other things (Udaya & Adibe, 2022). This is because, religions control human actions in both social, political, economic and otherwise.

However, for better understanding of the viewpoints here, we are going to look at the conceptual issues in Christian religion and education, most inevitable arbitrations, the teaching of Christian religious studies in Nigeria, and also make a critical analysis based on facts as presented. The conclusion and recommendations stands as a way forward.

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Conceptual Issues

The teaching of CRS dates back to the 19th century with the pioneers of Nigerian education (Ajogwu, 2016). But, following the governmental takeover of schools in Nigeria, secondary school curriculum was reviewed and more emphasis was placed on the studies of science and technological subjects. This shift was seen to have affected the study and interest of students in CRS in school system leading to poor enrollment in CRS. Bayeri (2015) stressed that student's poor enrollment and interest in CRS could as well be as a result of inadequate provision of teaching aids with reference to ICT, having fewer professional teachers and lack of incentives among other things. He opined that poor enrollment of students in CRS could be attributed to teacher's instructional delivery system and the teachers' personality. CRS is taught in all the senior secondary schools in Nigeria as an elective subject, while in colleges it is studied as a course of study, and also in the universities as an area of specialization. . The elective nature of the subject in Senior Secondary Schools in Nigeria had equally reduced the number of students that register for the subject in West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO), as well as other professional and internal examinations.

Referring to the relevance, CRS as a subject bases its teaching on the life and teaching of Jesus Christ. And, it ethical considerations stands film

as a teaching course, not only geared towards converting people to Christianity, but also necessary for value formation, value orientation and reorientation of value system as well as spiritual uplift of the people and students in particular (Elom, 2024). More so, it is observed that, CRS is a subject which aims at developing and fostering in the lives of the students the Christian attitudes and values such as respect to life, obedience to constituted authority, responsible self-reliance, and selfless service to God and humanity (Gaiya & Nwoko, 2022). To those in Christian religion, CRS is seen as an academic discipline that is designed to provide the learner with moral and spiritual transformation. This shows that CRS is the study of Christian lifestyles such as love, caring, patience, faith, forgiveness and hope in God as well as good relationship among men. It is equally clear from religious point of view that CRS, like every other subjects has five features. These features include; a set of rational theoretical formulation, inherent capacity for growth, applicable solution to human problems, organized Body of the knowledge and a degree of uniformity with other area of academic activities. Onwukwe (2013) observed that it will not be an overstatement to assert that without theological education, there would have been a great confusion concerning the interpretation of Christian belief and doctrine.

In the context of this study, CRS is defined as a social science subject that teaches students good behaviour, having the fearing of God, knowledge and skills that will make them to contribute their

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quota in socio-economic and moral development of the various communities in the world,. The inclusion of sound religious and moral values in the life of students invariably helps in the development of spiritual and moral soundness of the youths thereby producing the reasonable members of the society. These important values attached to the study of CRS in schools and colleges cannot be achieved if teachers in schools and other religious environment do not utilized effective teaching method that appeals to all the senses of their students and other listening audience when learning the morals in religion.

Inevitable Arbitrations

Following the shift in the study of CRS to other challenging areas in economy, motivation started dwindling and interest in the subject dropped. The continuous drop in the students' enrollment into this subject area shows that the teaching of the subject is witnessing slackening and control. Those in the schools and colleges are witnesses that Heads of Departments and principals /head teachers are having the difficulty of assigning teachers when placing the subject in the school timetable, seeing the teachers' lack of commitment and other defects such as students' dishonesty, examination malpractices and disrespect to mention but a few. In relation to the above, we often see that students nowadays are groomed to be intellectual giants in science and technology with little or no interest in the moral growth hereby resorting to spiritually dwarfism (Onah, 2020). And, more likely to say that when the children /youths grow older, they may create an avenue to

close or forget the spiritual vacuum owing to their not knowing the right attitude to life. Some of the students may join secret cults to perpetuate evil in diverse forms.

Remindful to note, the major aims of inclusion of CRS in the educational curriculum are farfetched. The central aim has been to raise generation of people who can think for themselves, respect the views and feelings of others, appreciate dignity of labour and strive for moral values specified in the broad national aims as necessities for good citizens (Gaiya, 2022). The truth remains that at the secondary school level, the subject is meant to prepare learners for useful living through inculcation of Christian attitudes and values, and to prepare learners for higher education. More reasonable to say is that the major factor in effective teaching of CRS must base on the professional preparation of the teachers. This teaching demands a lot of competencies on the side of the teacher in that excellence is required in manipulating instructional aids, assessment and management of instruction to ensure that the desired impact is made in the learner. This means that a CRS teacher in schools and other communities of faith is required to develop a coherent understanding of the pedagogical aims of the subject. It is only such teacher with appropriate religious professional formation or one who has clear vision of the Christian milieu; and lives in accordance with it that would be able to give the required inspiration needed to put into practice the moral essence required for the building of a nation (Opara, 2019). This implies that the

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commitment of the teacher is of immense importance in the curriculum implementation.

Take it and note that the teachers' integrity to faith and life is an approach to implementation of CRS curriculum. For instance, experience of God's mercy and love can go a long way in changing students' view or behaviour about one another. Majority of what happens in the life of a learner is being determined by the teachers' efficacy; therefore, it appears that the basic problem to effective teaching of CRS and morality has to do with the teachers' dispositions, hence reverting to ensuring the method of religious iconoclasm.

Teaching Christian Religion in Nigeria

Udaya (2015) cited Wikipedia free Encyclopedia when defining Christian religion as an academic field of multi-disciplinary, secular study of religious beliefs, behaviors, and institutions. He opined that religious study originated in the nineteenth century, when scholarly and historical analysis of the Bible had flourished, and Hindu and Buddhist texts were first being translated into European languages. He had noticed the early influential scholars in religion education to included Friedrich Max Muller in England and Cornelius P. Tiele in the Netherlands. This observation can be said to have described, compared, interpret, and explained religion with emphasizes to systematic, historically-based, and cross-cultural perspectives and focus of the subject area.

Recently, religious studies are taught and practiced worldwide. Christian religious knowledge is now a compulsory subject for

students in primary and junior secondary schools but made elective in most universities, schools and colleges. The subject is also taught at the senior secondary school level and in most religious centers. And, while theology attempts to understand God, religious studies exists to study human religion, behaviors and beliefs (Ugwa, 2022). Like other scholars, Opara (2022) classified the behavioural objectives of teaching and learning Christian religion into three categories which includes cognitive, affective and psychomotor. These are explained thus: objectives in the cognitive domain emphasize recall or recognition of facts, and the development of objectives of affective domain are concerned in changes in interest, attitudes and value, and the development of appreciation and judgment. Psychomotor domain objectives have to do with physical skills, manipulation of materials and objects.

When asking for the best method a teacher would apply while teaching his subject or course of study, it will take someone to the understanding that each person has his own talents, his strong point, and his weaknesses. For example, no teacher can use every method with equal success. Most teachers may use only one or two most effectively. And, the wise teacher is he who uses the method that bring best results. This is because, no good method is the best result of some clever inventions (Ebuoh, 2006). Hence, there are several methods that can be used effectively. These include both old and new methods. The methods are storytelling, lecture, discussion, the question and answer, the study

trip, the panel discussion, debate, the forum discussion, dramatization individualized, discovery, mimicking, pantomime and role play etc.

In order that teaching may be successful, a teacher is made to use teaching aids to support his method of teaching his subject area. Okorie (2021) stressed that students remember, 10% of what they read, 20% of what they hear, 30% of what they see, 50% of what they hear and see, 70% of what they say and 90% of what they see, hear, say and do. This information goes with the Old Chinese saying that “What I hear I forget; what I say I remember; what I do I know and understand”. This means that seeing and doing things will make a person know, understand and remember things learned best. Thus, let it appeal to the conscience that the essence of learning with visual materials for which we undermine in teaching Christian religion in Nigeria is a misnomer.

Back to Secondary school level, the Christian Religious Knowledge (CRK) syllabus is designed to enable learners to acquire an enduring but positive values. Some of the contents in the syllabus through which the expected values can be acquired are according to Aghaegbuna (1995) can be outlined but not limited to:

- i. Important values in human relationships which includes love, unity, forgiveness, endurance, peace, patience, cooperation, etc.
- ii. Sharing of hope, interest, and fear that teaches open-mindedness and friendliness and encourages students to share their hope, interest,

and fear with others rather than living a solitary life.

iii. A parable about our attitude to possessions including the parable of the rich fool, the rich man and Lazarus are related to learners. This is to teach about the danger of craze for wealth and the need for them to assist others with their possessions.

iv. The unfaithfulness of Ananias and Saphira. Students are to learn this story and bring out the moral lessons which include: danger of unfaithfulness, repercussion of lying, and the need for truthfulness’ unity and charity in the early church. This concept teaches the importance of unity among Christians. It also encourages learners to be hospitable by sharing whatever they have with others.

Religion education is another side of the same coin. It exists as a school subject since colonial era though with moral laxity. Ani & Mezieobi, (2022) noted that the question of effective, religious education in schools dominates our newspapers, magazines, symposiums, televisions and radios among others. Suffice it to say that the challenges facing religious education depends largely on many factors. The first and second factors are the teacher who teaches, and the student who is the recipient. The third factor is the method used in delivering the teaching. Going by this observation, it becomes clearer that the problems facing the teaching of Christian Religious Studies in the schools include but not limited to inadequate supply of qualified and competent Christian religious studies teachers, inadequate supply of instructional materials,

unconducive teaching environment, poor supervision, and Poor motivation from every higher or upper side to the Christian religious studies' teachers etc.

Durkheim Functionalist Theory

David Emile Durkheim (1858-1917), a French social scientist developed a functionalist theory otherwise referred to as functionalism. His interest was on how social order is possible or how society remains relatively stable. The theory focused on the macro level of social structure, rather than the micro level of everyday life. Functionalists believe that every prosperous and advanced society is based on a value consensus; a shared set of norms and values that everyone agrees on and is expected to commit to and enforce. Consensus values according to the theory helps to establish a common identity thereby building unity, cooperation and goals through a moral education. The theory identified society to be more important than the individual. And, from this perspective, disorganization in the system such as deviant behavior leads to change in social component which is made to always try to adjust so as to achieve stability. Also, by doing this, if all goes well, the parts of society would produce order, stability and productivity. But, if all does not go well, the parts of society must adapt to produce new forms of order, stability and productivity.

The implication of this theory is that when one part of the system is dysfunctional, it affects all other parts thereby creating social problems or changes. Applying this to the teaching, studying and the practice of Christian Religion (CRS/K),

one could argue that teachers play a crucial role in imparting religious values and knowledge, contributing to the moral and social stability within a community of faith, schools and colleges. Students and other practitioners demonstrate their ownership of this religion in their daily practices and equally in other activities.

However, Durkheim's theory suggests that teachers in CRS serve the function of reinforcing religious norms and values, thus contributing to the stability and integration of society through the transmission of religious teaching. Therefore, when the system becomes bad, they should go back to the drawing board via religious iconoclasm.

Critical Analysis

The question of why this rise in level of immorality among Christian students is yet unwavering. Educational body in Nigeria are owned by either private persons, cooperate organizations and/or the government, yet its managements is in standstill while the running at comatose. When many teachers are not helping, most graduates are not employable and living in the society are almost a mirage, there is need to run back to Christian religion. And, at our own corner, Christian religious iconoclasm is mostly needed to rewrite all wrongs as caused by religious corruptors.

Additionally, moral and religious education are both clearly defined areas of study where many philosophers, psychologists, religionist and other researchers have devoted most of their time to find and resolve many matters in various

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stages of moral and religious development . The way moral and religious education should be taught in Nigerian schools are basically in the contents, materials and activities, available for use in the moral and religious classes. For instance, it was specified that children should be guided not only to understand moral and religious principles but also their implications in different aspects of their daily lives and activities whether at work, rest, leisure or play. Again, that teaching is more successful in schools and colleges, especially, when a teacher would use teaching aids to support his method of teaching religious education. But, it is regrettable that despite all these regardless, most of these things are seen or kept in a paper work.

We often see Poor motivation of teachers. This is related to the old adage that teachers' rewards are in heaven. But, if the case of a teacher juxtaposes that of rich man and Lazarus' in the bible, how sure are we that every teacher will make heaven? (Luke 16; 19-31). It is clear that poor motivation of teachers and subsequent supervision may lead to bad teaching and unsuccessful information in schools and colleges. And, also to have a successful teaching and learning of Christian religious studies, a conducive environment is required; skills, and also employment based on qualification of teachers is also necessary.

On the other hand, we have been seen too often to forget that the acquisition of the principle of sound moral and religious education at schools will help the students to differentiate between morally acceptable behaviors from non-

acceptable ones. Even if any student may engage in immoral behavior in his late life, he/she may be able to know clearly whether what he is doing is good or bad. Again, it is baseless to leave out moral and religious education in the school time table because of possible mishandling by insufficiently informed teachers and a cause from the other side of school owners or managers.

Lastly, we often see people placing and praising law over morality as against the theological education for the building of societies. Let it be on record that St. Paul in one of his prison epistle wrote to Timothy that any doctrine which tries to rise against theological education would only cause disputes rather than godly edification which is in faith. Law to him is not made for a person whose concern is righteousness but for the lawless and insubordinate, for the ungodly and sinners, for the unholy and profane, for murderers of fathers and murderers of mothers, for fornicators, for sodomites, for kidnappers, for manslayers, for liars, for perjurers, and also if there is any other thing that is contrary to sound doctrine (1 Timothy 1:5-10).

Conclusion

The country Nigeria has grown so big to tackle some of its educational problems but still lacks behind in some aspects. This study has highlighted the problems, causes, and possible solution to immoral living among Christian religion students. From the findings, it has been observed that bad teachers, lack of instructional materials, use of old or outdated curriculum, school owners' cum managerial syndrome, and

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several influences from students and people in other religions are some of the causes of this menace. Furthermore, options for solving this problems has been highlighted following the analysis of the concept of Christian religion, from its contents or embodiments to the teaching, supervision, and also the benefits in owning, knowing, teaching, learning and the practice of this subject area or specialization (CRS). Therefore, going back to the original information on Christian religion as a student, teacher or practitioner via religious iconoclasm is the nearest option.

Recommendations

The following recommendations where drafted out based on the findings:

1. The government should establish a well-disciplined team to monitor the teaching methods employed in schools and colleges.
2. The teachers should adhere to the curriculum and use of instructional materials when teaching the subject or course of study.
3. The government and other owners of education should assist the teachers through reasonable payment, and availing instructional materials, audio visual and other aids in teaching and learning of CRS.
4. There should be a conducive environment for learning and practice of the subject area or course of study.
5. More research should be conducted to understand the many reasons behind people's unruly behaviours, during or when, and also after graduating from schools and colleges.

6. Therefore, to him who knows to do good thing and does not do it, to him it is counted as sin. (James 4:17)

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